

LIFE OF WORD DURING CORONAVIRUS

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Nowadays the problem of neologisms is one of the actual issues. Many linguists have reflected this problem in their works. Let's say, E.V. Senko has a number of works, considering innovations in the modern Russian language. He involves specific time parameters, considering these parameters in the interlevel aspect and raising the theoretical foundations of neology. For example, neologisms of the modern Russian language at the end of the XX century [1: 50; 2: 107; 3: 356].

The problem of neologisms based on metaphorization and metonymization is presented in the work of N.V. Chernikova [5: 82]. The issues of neology with the involvement of metaphorization in the German language also received worthy coverage: G. Lüdi «Metapher und Neologismus» [7: 18], and in French the problem of typological characteristics of

ABSTRACT

The article analyzes the neologisms that appeared during the coronavirus pandemic. The article is based on lively factual material with the involvement of different languages: Russian, German, French, and Hebrew. The authors made the attempt to reveal the functional-systemic relationships that have developed on the basis of new words, stable word-groups associated with the thematic field of coronavirus infection. The most widely-spread definitions of neologisms are presented in the work. The article deals with the issues of derivational orientation. The analysis was carried out from the point of view of the emotional and expressive characteristics of the neof ormations.

neologisms is well developed on the basis of two styles: colloquial and business through the prism of both linguistic and sociolinguistic aspect [4: 272]. Moreover, in the system of realization of stylistic probability, neologisms were considered in the work of V.E. Yarnatovskaya [6: 178-182].

Our work is related to the issues of neologization during the period of coronavirus infection. New words and stable word-groups or so-called "corona" expressions have appeared in different languages in connection with the coronavirus pandemic. This is primarily due to the emergence of new realities in our life. In addition to the formation of neologisms, there is a phenomenon of rethinking the old meaning of words and stable word-groups that has already functioned in the language

(«корона», «социальная дистанция», «самоизоляция» in Russian), as well as medical professional terms with a highly specialized meaning have become actively used in the common language (ALV - artificial lung ventilation. A medical device designed for supplying a gas mixture consisting of oxygen and compressed dried air to the lungs to saturate the blood with oxygen, as well as to remove carbonic acid from the lungs, a strain - a collection of organisms of the same species with similar properties. There can be many strains of coronavirus. They can mutate in different organisms) ... For instance, Czech linguists have identified over eighty words that contain the corona component, and most of them begin with this component [8]. Many of these new formations have negative connotations.

Such type of formations appeared in Russian, French, English, German, Hebrew and other languages. Moreover, these can be words and expressions that are not necessarily associated with the lexeme corona, but also those that are united by this topic. Ср:

- in Russian language: коронакризис (coronacrisis), корона-детки (coronababies), коронапаника (coronapanic), ковид-развод, or ковидиворс (covidivors), коронавирусная инфекция (coronavirus infection), «китайская инфекция» («Chinese infection»), «уханьский вирус» "Wuhan virus", карантейнджеры (quaranteenagers), коронаэпидемия (corona-epidemic), ковидиот (covidiot) or коронаидиот (coronaidiot), or ковид-диссидент (ВИЧ/СПИД-дессиденты) (covid-dissident (HIV/AIDS dissidents)), ковидиотизм (covidiotism), коронаскептики (coronasceptics),

самоизоляция (self-isolation), «школа в пижаме» («school in pajamas» (distance learning)), социальное дистанцирование (social distancing), коронадепрессия (coronadepression), карантинные меры (quarantine measures), коронафейки (coronafakes). By the way, the spelling of the term coronavirus through a is explained by the origin of this term by borrowing from English to Russian. Wed: папилломавирус (papillomavirus), ротавирус (rotavirus).

- in French language: the emergence of the neologism skypero (or a variant of skypéro) is connected with the French tradition, when friends get together in order to drink before dinner and communicate. Ср: in Russian скайперо (aperitif via Skype due to coronavirus. By the way, Internet dictionaries that respond more quickly to neology already record this word, so it has a page in Wikionnaire. Ср. another neologism of this type: whatsapero (virtual aperitif via video link in WhatsApp). The neologism coronanniversaire (ср. коронаверсеп in Russian) was formed by a method of addition based on two words: coronavirus and anniversaire (anniversary, birthday). This word is polysemantic: 1) the birthday is celebrated through a video conference, relatives and friends congratulate the birthday boy; 2) birthday alone. The neologism le zumping is associated with parting in French, formed by the method of addition, namely: Zoom and dumping.

- in German language: Abstrichzentrum (smear center where you can take a coronavirus test), Corona-Krise (crown-crisis), Corona-Hysterie (crown-hysteria), Coronioia (paranoia), Corona-Partys (corona-parties), Corona-Babys (coronababies), Coronials, Corona-Bonds, Corona-

Abitur (corona-exam for matriculation certificate), zoomen (distance work in the form of video conference by using ZOOM), Gabenzaun, (fence, which is used in order to hang products and things for those in need), the phraseological unit (PU) Home Office ('work at home' is a meaning in German language, the source of which was the English phraseological unit with the meaning «Department of the Interior»).

Neologisms of similar subject matter enter into different relations from the point of view of systemic relations. For example, the synonym for the word quarantine is the lexeme *cornteen*, which has an ironic connotation and arose on the basis of the words *coronavirus* and *quarantine*. *Ковид*, *корона*, *коронарка* are synonyms of the same COVID-19 infection, which is similar in structure to the solar crown. *Удалёнка* (telecommuting) is work from home, to which many organizations have transferred employees due to the need to comply with quarantine. This also includes distance learning in schools and universities. Ср.: *Дистант* (distant) - distance learning for schoolchildren. The same as *удаленка* (telecommuting) only for children. For example, the lexeme *коронаэнтузиасты* (corona-enthusiasts) enters into an antonymic relationship with the words of *коронаскептики* (coronasceptics) and *ковид-диссиденты* (covid-dissidents). By the way, there are also humorous formations of the type of *погулянцы* and *сидидомцы* in antonymic relations, which occupy directly opposite positions on the implementation of quarantine measures.

Interesting puns (the so-called wordplay) appeared. Thus, the well-known stable expression «скоротать время» (pass the time) as a result of a pun was transformed

into *скарантинить время* (pass the time during quarantine), and the second component remains in the unchanged form «время» (time), while the first component the verb *скарантинить* is formed from the noun *карантин* (quarantine) with the prefix *с* attached and has something in common with the stable phrase *скоротать время* (pass the time).

The words and expressions that have appeared are characterized by an emotionally-expressive coloring. They convey our feelings, emotions, moods, desires, i.e. our attitude to what is happening, to reality. New words and stable word-groups help the interlocutors express themselves more vividly and at the same time more meaningfully.

The meaning of neoformations with the topic of coronavirus mainly has a negative connotation. These can be rough words, such as: *карантец*, *ковидло*, *ковидиот* or *коронаидиот* or whole expressions, such as: *цифровой концлагерь*, *подцепить корону* (where the components of *концлагерь* and *подцепить* are clearly associated with negative), *локдаун* (youth slang of Russians) means quarantine during the coronavirus. The origin is associated with downtime for hockey players in battle. The lexeme *coronanoia* (ср. Russian *коронное* - a synonym for the expression of *paranoia* in coronavirus), associated with a state of psychic in which the slightest cough and sneeze is perceived as a coronavirus infection, carries an explicit negative. This word has a variant - *pararona*. The word *ковидный* has a connotation of contempt for the meaning 'contagious'.

So, the meaning of the word *ковидиот* is associated with the reaction of some people to the coronavirus pandemic. The

word ковидиот comes from the contraction of the two words ковид and идиот. The law of haplology applies in this case, when the same part of the roots overlaps. Ср. from минералология the word минералогия was formed, similarly from ковидоидиот was formed ковидиот. This lexeme is popular thanks to the play of words. Ср. Covidiot in English (from Covid-19 and idiot). This word has two opposite connotations in the meaning. On the one hand, this is a person, who is negligent and disdainful of the recommendations of doctors, and on the other hand, this is a person who on the contrary is too panicky, causing unnecessary fear by his actions. These meanings have a common points of convergence, namely: ковидиот is a person who behaves like an idiot in these situations. So, there were such examples: «Вы видели того ковидиота с 300 рулонами туалетной бумаги в тележке?» and «Эта ковидиотка обнимает каждого, кого увидит». The lexeme coronadouche (ср. Russian коронадурки) means 'to sell your stock at a huge premium'. There is a big difference between these words. So, ковидиоты behave this way because of fear, but коронадурки do it quite deliberately. There is a phenomenon of stigmatization (hanging social labels, associating a quality with an individual or a set of people, although this connection is absent or not proven). Ср: китайская инфекция, уханьский вирус. There is clearly a negative attitude contained in the components of the infection and the virus. Another stable expression that is known to us, but which has acquired an additional shade of meaning, is the mask show. There are notes of causticity of those, who consider wearing masks useless in the

current situation. Sarcasm can also be traced in the meaning of the lexeme маскобесие. However, the rules of at least minimal protection and humane treatment of surrounding people still exist.

However, there are also positive attitude from a stylistic point of view. For example, a clearly positive assessment is contained in the lexeme карантикулы, which has an ironic connotation, formed from the phrase holidays caused by the need to be in quarantine. The new phrase школа в пижаме (school in pajamas (distance learning)) also has a positive connotation - playfulness, the so-called domestication of danger. Moreover, the term карантинки helps us go through the alarming situation of the pandemia.

Formed from the lexeme валентинки, it is associated with funny couplets that lovers exchange during separation due to quarantine. There is a hint of playfulness here, with the help of which we try to have a positive attitude, and perceive what is happening in a positive perspective. According to the principle of formation мартини with the use of the lexeme карантин, the name of the alcoholic drink карантини was formed, in the original form it contains vodka, whiskey and necessarily strong liquor (from the English quarantini, invented by the creators of the movie "Clinic"). People began to widely use lexis similar to such as: «сидидомцы и погулянцы».

New professions have appeared, for example, карантье - are people who can rent out their dogs in order to provide the opportunity for other people to walk along the street and not receive a fine while walking during the quarantine period. Ср: рантье - a person living on interest of the

capital lent out. From income from securities (shares, bonds).

The lexeme корониалы, i.e. children who quickly adapted to new conditions to live and work in the virtual world, appeared in colloquial speech. They help parents adapt to new conditions. For example, set up the ZOOM program. The second meaning of this lexeme, formed by analogy with миллениалы. Children who were conceived during a pandemia.

In connection with the pandemia, the word хомяк from the German word Hamster has become widely used, the Swedes use hamstra. This metaphor is associated with the meaning of making large purchases in store. By the way, in the German language there is a lexeme Hamsterkäufe (people buying a huge number of essential items for all occasions and putting these products at home), i.e. so-called hamster purchases. Moreover, the word Hamstern is used to mean 'purchasing large quantities of food and scarce goods for future use'.

There is clearly a shade of irony in the lexeme коронавты. When we see a person in a mask, gloves, goggles, closed shoes and clothing, it is associated with an astronaut.

It is interesting that the Hebrew Academy of Language was forced to compile a terminological dictionary related to the coronavirus in order to instruct inhabitants of Israel to correctly pronounce and use neologisms in their speech that arose during the pandemia.

Tamar Trabelsi-Hadad, the author of the Ynet website, introduced readers with this dictionary, which contains the special vocabulary of the coronavirus. For example, in this dictionary they specify which verb is appropriate when putting on a mask: lovshim, samim, otim. From the

point of view of the Academy, the correct option would be "ata", "laatot" (לעטות, עטה).

There are certain fine points, the knowledge of which sheds light on the emergence of certain terms. So, names are given to diseases in Hebrew, but viruses are usually ignored. However, the coronavirus has so strongly affected the daily life of the Earthlings that it even violated the established traditions and rules. Therefore, even Israeli academics believe that an exception to the rule is quite possible, and a neologism with the name of a new virus will appear in Hebrew. It also depends on how long the coronavirus will disturb us and violate our usual way of life.

Residents of Israel offer their options, arguing their choice, and send them to the Academy. For example, coronavirus (negif ha-korona, הקורונה נגיף), cateret (פִּתְרֵת) - from the word ceter, corona, carenet (קֶרֶנֶת) - from the word ceren (ray) or nazeret (נִזְרֵת) - from the word nezer, tiara. The word virus, which has the name negif (נְגִיף), is proposed to be replaced by the word magefa (מַגְפָּה), which means 'epidemic', i.e. disease leading to the death of a large number of people.

Thus, the Official Dictionary of the Coronavirus of the Hebrew Language Academy includes the following terms: Magefa (מַגְפָּה) - an epidemic, an infectious disease that affects a large number of people; Magefa olamit, Magefa rabati (מַגְפָּה עוֹלָמִית, מַגְפָּה רַבָּתִי) - a pandemic, a global epidemic; Negif (נְגִיף) is a virus that can reproduce only inside living cells; Mahala midabeket (מַחֲלָה מִדַּבְּקֵת) - contagious disease; Tasmin (תַּסְמִינִיּוֹן) is a symptom; Lelo tasminim (לֵלוֹ תַסְמִינִים) - no symptoms, asymptomatic

carrier; Bidud (בִּידוּד) - isolation; Esger (הֶסְגֵר) - quarantine;
Seger (סִגָר) - blocking of a settlement or region, including a ban on leaving it;
Matosh (מָטוֹשׁ) - a cotton bud for taking a swab from the nose to analyze for the presence of the virus; Hisun (הִסוּן) - vaccination, immunization, inoculation;
Trufat deme, placebo (דְּמָה תְרוּפֹת) - a placebo, a substance that mimics a drug effect; Du-alum (עֲלוּם-דוּ) - a double-blind method, an experiment in which two groups of infected persons participate, one of which receives the real medicine, and the other - placebo; Maarikhi (מַעְרִיכִי) - exponential (growth); Tavkhela (תַּבְהֵלָה) - panic; Melonit (מְלוֹנִית) - a hotel in a medical institution or repurposed to isolate virus carriers.

Some dictionaries have already included words related to Covid-19. Thus, the third edition of the Oxford English Dictionary (OED) includes neologisms related to coronavirus infection. Similarly, neologisms are included into the Neomat (database of new expressions), produced by the Institute of Language at the Czech Academy.

For example, the neologism term Covid-19 is interpreted by lexicographers as "Acute respiratory disease of people, caused by the coronavirus, which can cause severe symptoms and death, especially among the elderly and other people with chronic diseases" [9].

The OED includes the term infodemia, which has the following meaning: "the dissemination of diverse, often unsubstantiated information related to a crisis, controversy or event that spreads rapidly and uncontrollably through news, online and social media and is considered

as reinforcing public speculation or anxiety" [9].

The OED neologism self-isolation is defined as "an act, fact or process of deliberate isolation. Voluntary isolation undertaken in order to avoid infection or transmitting an infectious disease, or as part of a public initiative to prevent its spread" [9].

In connection with the emergence of new words, phrases and new meanings, it became necessary to define them. So, the words quarantine and self-isolation, which are similar in subject matter, have significant differences in meaning. Quarantine is a complete isolation regime, in which it is generally not allowed to leave the room in which you live. In case of self-isolation, residents can leave their home if necessary (visiting a doctor, buying medicine, food, walking the dog, work). Moreover, people who have come into contact with patients with coronavirus or who have arrived from abroad are placed in quarantine. However, both words are associated with a common problem: to stop the spread of infection. The word observation, which is something between self-isolation and quarantine, can be attributed to such a lexical-semantic field. This is a special kind of measure in relation to those people "who cannot be at home, and they do not need hospitalization. They are placed in specially designated places - observation centers."

Considerable interest is also associated with the grammatical characteristics of the emerging neologisms. For example, linguists in France said that COVID-19 is female. French linguists proceed from the fact that the category of gender in formations by the type of abbreviation is determined by the main word, which in this case is feminine. The lexeme disease -

maladie (féminin) in French is feminine. However, the difficulty is that this term is borrowed from the English term Coronavirus disease. "The French Academy, which defends the correct use of the French language, recommends the use of the word COVID-19 in feminine rather than masculine, whereas even in most cases the use of this term in France since the appearance of the coronavirus has been associated with masculine gender."

Due to the popularity of the application for video conferencing ZOOM and its wide use in holding various kinds of events (seminars, meetings, dissertation defense in special councils, teaching students and schoolchildren, dating, parties, quizzes, games, etc.), words such as зум, зум-вечеринка, зумить, зум-свадьба. зумер, зумификация, зумиться, зумбомбинг, tautological expression, зумеры зумятся. Ср: зумер - originally a person belonging to generation Z, but after зумификации in everything (that is, switching to the Zoom program) - those who spend a lot of time in video conferencing using the Zoom online platform. Obviously, the verbal lexeme зумить is formed from the noun зум according to the model зум → зумить by analogy with гугл → гуглить, and зумиться - according to the model of чатиться.

The neologisms that have appeared refer to different parts of speech. The analyzed material showed that the majority are nouns. Ср.: дистанционка (distance learning), думскроллинг (scrolling through the scary news from doom – death and scroll – turn over), инфодемия - information epidemic (slang).

The growth of the flow of information about the epidemic, often false and exaggerated, fake), ковидник (a hospital

for patients with COVID or the patient himself), Коммунарка (a Russian coronavirus hospital, previously intended for a hospital with cancer and as a center for women's health), контагиозность (infectiousness, as the main property of coronavirus, rapid transmission of the virus from a patient to a healthy person and through the surfaces on which it settles), курьеры (people working in the delivery service), обсервация (isolation under medical supervision with strict restrictions), пандемия (a disease that has massive character).

According to the WHO criteria, a пандемия is the spread of a new disease on a global scale), патогенность (the ability of an infectious agent (a strain of a microorganism or a virus) to generate pathologies, diseases and deviations from the norm), плато (information of a statistical character about Covid-19, when there is no increase in the number of infected people. It is displayed on the graph as a straight line), погулявцы (people in favor of soft quarantine), самоизоляция (a regime in which (as in quarantine), there are bans, but on a voluntary basis.

Карантин is an official prohibition), санитайзер (disinfecting liquid or hand sanitizer), сатурация (blood oxygen saturation is the main parameter that the pulse oximeter determines), сидимомцы (people in favor of strict quarantine), суперспредер (суперраспространитель) (a person who refuses to comply with the self-isolation regime and infecting everyone around), тепловизор (a device for instantaneous temperature measurement. Currently it is widely used in public places), удалёнка (remote work), фомит (an object that can become a threat of infection. For example, things that have

recently been touched by an infected person), шашлычники (self-isolation violators who arrange picnics) [10].

However, adjectives related to the new situation appeared. For example, ковидный (about covid hospital/patient), подозрительные (medical term for patients with suspected COVID-19), масочно-перчаточный (режим) (mask and glove (regime)) and substantiated participles, euphemism коронованный (a person infected with a coronavirus), контактные (people in contact with coronavirus people or those who returned from abroad and placed in home quarantine), the adverb вжоперти is roughly colloquial (ср: взаперти (locked up)) - a play on words.

There are such stable word-groups as: группы риска (risk groups) (these are people who are most susceptible to severe coronavirus infection: elderly people over 60 years old, people with chronic diseases), красная зона (red zone) (danger zone (in a hospital, city, district)), i.e. a place, where are the carriers of the coronavirus), нулевой пациент (zero patient) (the first infected patient in the population of the epidemiological study), онлайн-вечеринки (online parties) (a party in the zoom), социальное дистанцирование (social distancing) (a measure to reduce contact with other people, maintaining a two-meter distance), условно положительный результат (a conditionally positive result) (a positive result gives one test carried out). However, for an accurate result, it is necessary to carry out three tests with observance of time intervals, hence the word is условно (conditional), цифровой концлагерь (a digital concentration camp) (something that should have come with the

introduction in Moscow and some regions of the system of electronic passes to exit outside during quarantine according to the opposition), цифровой пропуск (digital pass) (QR-code) (a set of numbers, without which you cannot leave home far), шведский сценарий (the Swedish scenario) (a scenario in which the state does not introduce quarantine in order to develop collective immunity).

As a result of the pandemic, numerous abbreviations have entered our lives. For example, FFP 1,2 (types of respirators that are used along with masks as a means of protection, but for a longer time from 6 to 8 hours), SARS-CoV-2 (scientific designation of a new coronavirus, the pathogen that causes Covid-19), ПЦР (the test system - a Russian method for diagnosing coronavirus, where ПЦР is a polymerase chain reaction that helps to identify the type of virus and its concentration. In spoken language, палка в нос (a stick in the nose), since the test is taken from the back of the nasopharynx with a long stick), СИЗы - средства индивидуальной защиты (personal protective equipment: masks, gloves, glasses), Covid-19 (abbreviation from the English COronaVirus Disease 2019, that is coronavirus infection), etc.

Conclusion.

1. The emergence of new words and stable word-groups in different languages of the world are associated with the current situation in the world - the coronavirus pandemic.
2. This trend is based on the emergence of new realities in the life around us. New professions, new devices and new alcoholic beverages have appeared.

3. Linguistic neoformations are associated with the rethinking of already existing meanings.

4. Many highly specialized terms have become widely used.

5. Neologisms may have a corona component in their composition, however, there are formations that do not include this component, but are associated with a similar theme.

6. Compilers of electronic dictionaries have an amazing ability to replenish the dictionary with new words and expressions constantly and timely.

7. Neologisms of this topic enter into different relationships: synonymous, antonymic, polysemantic from the point of view of systemic relations.

8. The emerging neologisms also have their own characteristics from the point of view of grammar. In this case, the problems of the generic affiliation of new words appear. These formations refer to different parts of speech as the analysis has shown. However, the majority are nouns. Moreover, there are adjective, verbal, adverbial formations, as well as numerous stable word-groups.

9. Most of new formations arose as a result of compounding from the point of view of derivation. The abbreviation is typical for most languages, The formation of neologisms with a similar theme also occurs as a result of substantiation.

10. Most neologisms associated with coronavirus infection have a negative assessment in terms of connotation. However, positive characteristics are present in some lexemes and stable word-groups, which is associated with psychological aspects: the desire to overcome the fear of uncertainty, illness and even death. Therefore, neoformations appeared with a shade of playfulness and irony. A pun as a device is often used.

11. Linguists believe that neologisms related to the topic of coronavirus will probably linger in our vocabulary to our great regret but with the hope that they will move from active vocabulary to passive vocabulary with the end of the pandemic. There appears the desire to transfer them into the category of words-meteors.

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